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Rank	Institution	Last 12 Months				All Time				Authors			
		Total New Downloads	# of New Papers	New Downloads per paper	Total # of Downloads	Total # of Citations	# of Papers	Total Downloads per paper	Total Citations per paper	# of Authors	Total Downloads per author	New Downloads per author	Total Citations per author
1	Humboldt University of Berlin - School of Business and Economics :: Germany	Authors 12,523 (50)	174 (1)	19 (258)	97,765 (62)	1,604 (55)	663 (37)	147 (312)	2 (122)	88 (58)	1,111 (151)	142 (124)	18 (78)
2	Srinivas Institute of Management Studies :: India	Authors 4,332 (116)	171 (2)	25 (174)	4,333 (515)	0 (936)	171 (152)	25 (533)	0 (378)	31 (186)	140 (648)	140 (125)	0 (506)
3	UNSW Business School :: Australia	Authors 45,687 (6)	152 (3)	24 (183)	460,578 (5)	7,228 (12)	1,940 (1)	237 (151)	4 (46)	358 (2)	1,287 (115)	128 (146)	20 (71)
4	Singapore Management University :: Singapore	Authors 41,843 (7)	127 (4)	30 (121)	359,067 (10)	5,712 (18)	1,382 (12)	260 (125)	4 (46)	277 (5)	1,296 (112)	151 (106)	21 (64)
5	KU Leuven - Faculty of Business and Economics (FEB) :: Belgium	Authors 19,467 (28)	114 (5)	10 (465)	189,727 (34)	6,724 (15)	1,939 (2)	98 (440)	3 (74)	387 (1)	490 (376)	50 (442)	17 (84)
6	University of Toronto - Rotman School of Management :: Canada	Authors 67,465 (4)	113 (6)	42 (50)	594,476 (3)	9,897 (5)	1,601 (6)	371 (51)	6 (21)	192 (18)	3,096 (20)	351 (14)	52 (16)
7	University of Melbourne - Faculty of Business and Economics :: Australia	Authors 23,133 (25)	112 (7)	13 (394)	272,340 (18)	5,737 (17)	1,762 (4)	155 (296)	3 (74)	249 (9)	1,094 (161)	93 (233)	23 (55)
8	Monash Business School :: Australia	Authors 24,929 (22)	101 (8)	18 (278)	219,530 (29)	1,325 (64)	1,371 (14)	160 (290)	1 (217)	299 (3)	734 (262)	83 (264)	4 (256)
9	Deakin University - Faculty of Business and Law :: Australia	Authors 12,778 (48)	99 (9)	20 (243)	72,474 (83)	493 (118)	649 (38)	112 (405)	1 (217)	134 (33)	541 (348)	95 (229)	4 (256)
10	City University London - Sir John Cass Business School :: United Kingdom	Authors 38,931 (8)	90 (10)	28 (136)	397,253 (7)	10,667 (4)	1,377 (13)	288 (98)	8 (7)	195 (16)	2,037 (49)	200 (58)	55 (14)
11	London Business School :: United Kingdom	Authors 72,841 (2)	89 (11)	40 (53)	822,573 (2)	15,890 (1)	1,840 (3)	447 (24)	9 (6)	230 (11)	3,576 (13)	317 (19)	69 (8)
11	Copenhagen Business School ::	Authors 57,807 (5)	89 (11)	39 (57)	434,690 (6)	7,942 (9)	1,470 (10)	296 (89)	5 (29)	270 (6)	1,610 (76)	214 (50)	29 (39)

